

CHANGES MACRO AND MICRO ELEMENT LEVELS IN MELON GENETIC RESOURCES GROWN UNDER DROUGHT CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT. Drought stress, an increasingly prevalent abiotic factor due to global climate change, poses a significant threat to agricultural productivity, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions. This study investigated changes in macro and micronutrient concentrations of 15 melon (*Cucumis melo* L.) genotypes subjected to drought conditions to evaluate their tolerance mechanisms. The genotypes, selected from diverse genetic resources across Türkiye, were grown hydroponically under controlled climate conditions using 8% polyethylene glycol (PEG 6000) to simulate drought stress. Nutrient analyses were conducted on root and shoot tissues, focusing on macro (P, K, Ca, Mg, S) and micro (Fe, Zn, Mn, B, Cu) elements. The results demonstrated considerable variation among genotypes in their response to drought. On average, phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), and sulfur (S) exhibited the most significant reductions among macronutrients. At the same time, manganese (Mn), zinc (Zn), iron (Fe), and copper (Cu) were the most affected micro-elements. The drought-sensitive genotype 'Kav 20' observed the most pronounced nutrient decreases. In contrast, genotypes 'Kav 248' and 'Kav 265' showed better retention of essential nutrient levels under stress, indicating higher tolerance. Furthermore, genotypes 'Kav 183' and 'Kav 190' were more negatively impacted due to significant Fe and Zn concentrations decline. These findings highlight the critical role of nutrient retention, particularly of Fe, Zn, and Mn, in drought stress resilience. Differences in the ability of melon genotypes to maintain adequate nutrient levels under stress conditions suggest that nutrient homeostasis is closely linked to drought tolerance. The results contribute valuable insights for selecting and developing drought-resilient melon cultivars through physiological and nutritional profiling.

Keywords: Melon, Drought stress, Plant nutrition, Macroelements, Microelements

INTRODUCTION

Melon (*Cucumis melo* L.) is an open-pollinated and diploid ($2n = 2x = 24$) plant belonging to the Cucurbitaceae family. It produces aromatic fruits, with global cultivation covering approximately 1,092,354 hectares and yielding 29.5 million tons [1]. As an annual plant with a long, trailing stem covered in fine hairs, melon has an unlimited growth capacity and continuously produces numerous branches [2]. Generally cultivated in the Mediterranean region and various parts of the world, this plant is affected by abiotic stress factors such as drought, high temperature [3], and salinity [4]. Although melon shows moderate tolerance to drought, it is grown in many regions of Türkiye, where drought is potentially a concern. Environmental factors like drought, which have emerged due to global climate change, have led to a decrease in yield in melon cultivation in recent years. While some cultural practices can be implemented to mitigate these stress factors, such measures are often limited, costly, and time-consuming. Therefore, developing drought-resistant varieties offers a more sustainable solution in the long term.

Global climate change is leading to severe droughts worldwide, placing significant pressure on agriculture and making the fight against hunger and the effort to ensure food security

increasingly tricky [4]. Drought is one of the main abiotic stress factors that restrict plant growth, development, and yield, reducing agricultural productivity by up to 50% [6, 7]. Rising temperatures, excessive use of natural resources, depletion of water sources, and the rapidly growing global population, which increase food demand, further exacerbate the effects of drought on agriculture [8]. Plants have developed various adaptation and tolerance mechanisms to support their growth under different stress conditions [9]. Under drought conditions, as the water potential between the leaves and the soil decreases, plants reduce transpiration by closing their stomata to minimize water loss, and they also develop adaptive changes in their root systems to absorb more nutrients from the soil [10].

Drought stress is an environmental stress factor that significantly reduces productivity and poses a significant barrier to agricultural production, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions. In this context, farmers are often compelled to increase irrigation frequency to mitigate the effects of drought stress. Water stress arises when the rate of transpiration exceeds the rate of water uptake, leading to reduced water absorption due to decreased water availability in the soil [11]. Drought stress affects various aspects of plant growth and physiology, reducing photosynthesis, respiration, and overall yield [12].

Plants respond to drought stress in various ways. These responses include stomatal closure, reduced net photosynthesis and transpiration, decreased water potential in plant tissues, and the accumulation of mechanisms such as abscisic acid (ABA), proline, glycine betaine, polyphenols, mannitol, sorbitol, antioxidant enzymes, and protein synthesis [13]. Additionally, drought stress has been shown to decrease nutrient element concentrations in melon leaves, particularly causing potassium and calcium levels to drop to insufficient levels [14]. Similar studies have reported that drought significantly reduces the concentrations of N, P, K, Ca, and Mg in tomato leaves [15]. It has also been observed that drought exposure in tomato and wheat plants leads to a decline in both macro- and micronutrient contents in the leaves [16, 17]. In tomatoes, drought negatively affects water use efficiency, enzyme function, nutrient uptake, and soluble sugar content [18]. Another significant impact of drought stress is generating reactive oxygen species (ROS). ROS damage macromolecules, membrane proteins, and lipids; however, plants attempt to mitigate the harmful effects of ROS by enhancing their antioxidant defense systems, such as catalase and peroxidase activity [9].

This study aims to examine the changes in macro and micronutrient elements in melon genotypes exposed to drought stress and to evaluate the resistance mechanisms exhibited by melons under these stress conditions. Drought stress leads to biochemical, physiological, and morphological changes in plants, significantly reducing productivity and adversely affecting mineral nutrition. Macro- and micronutrients play a crucial role in plant growth, development, and responses to environmental stresses. In this context, the study investigates how drought stress alters nutrient uptake and the biological functions of these elements in plants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In a previous study [19], a drought tolerance screening was conducted on 192 melon genotypes provided from various regions of Turkey and the world, as part of a collection developed by the Department of Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture, Çukurova University. From these genotypes, 15 (Kav 8, Kav 265, Kav 267, Kav 231, Kav 62, Kav 190, Kav 204, Kav 257, Kav 183, Kav 28, Kav 210, Kav 248, Kav 70, Kav 20, Kav 188), which had been identified as having tolerance traits under drought conditions, were selected for this research.

The melon genotypes used as research material were grown under controlled conditions in a growth chamber using a hydroponic system. In the chamber, the seeds and young seedlings of the plants used in the study were grown under controlled conditions set to 45–55% humidity,

a 16-hour light / 8-hour dark photoperiod, a temperature of $21\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, and a light intensity of 16,000 lux/day throughout their growth and development stages.

Seed Planting and Drought Application

The seeds of the melon genotypes used in the experiment were first treated with sodium hypochlorite, followed by 75% ethanol, then rinsed with sterile distilled water to complete surface sterilization. The sterilized seeds were soaked in distilled water for 4–5 hours. After germination in the dark at 22°C for three days, the germinated seedlings were grown in sterilized pots containing one-fifth strength Hoagland solution (control group). In addition to the control group (Hoagland solution), drought stress groups were created by adding a PEG 6000 solution prepared at 8% concentration to the Hoagland solution. The experiment was set up in four replications, with 10 plants per replication.

Determination of Nutrient Element Contents

Plant samples were collected from the root and stem tissues for nutrient element analysis 20 days after sowing, when the plants had reached the 6–7 leaf stage. After harvest, the vegetative parts of the plants brought to the laboratory in paper bags were washed thoroughly with tap water, followed by one rinse with distilled water, one rinse with 0.2 N HCl solution, two more rinses with distilled water, and a final rinse with deionized water. Excess moisture was removed using coarse filter paper. Each plant part was placed in a separate paper bag and dried to a constant weight at 70°C in a forced-air drying oven. After weighing the dried plant samples, they were ground in a tungsten-coated plant grinding mill. The ground samples were placed in polyethylene jars and left in the drying oven at 70°C until they reached a constant weight, after which the lids were tightly sealed.

A 0.3 g portion of the dried, ground plant sample was digested with 5 mL of HNO_3 using a microwave digestion system (CEM Mars 5) under high temperature (210°C) and pressure (200 PSI). The digested solution was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask, cooled, and made up to volume with deionized water. These solutions were immediately filtered through fine-pore filter paper (Whatman No. 42 or blue band) and transferred to 25 ml polyethylene bottles. The macro- and micronutrient contents of the filtrates were determined using an Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometer (ICP-AES) (Varian Vista, axial) [20].

Statistical Analyses

Minitab Statistical Software was used for the statistical calculations in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Changes in Macro Nutrient Elements

This study investigated melon genotypes' changes in the stem and root macronutrient contents (P, K, Ca, Mg, S) under drought stress conditions. Based on the average results, it was determined that under drought conditions, the most significant reductions in macronutrient content compared to the control occurred in the phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and sulfur (S) levels in both the stem and root (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Average reduction rates of Macronutrients in Stem parts based on the mean of melon genotypes

Fig. 2. Average reduction rates of Macronutrients in Root parts based on the mean of melon genotypes

The stem parts of the melon genotypes used in the study had a phosphorus (P) content that decreased by 24% under drought conditions (0.59% P) compared to the control (0.81% P). Among the melon genotypes, the most significant reduction in phosphorus content under drought conditions compared to the control was observed in genotype Kav 20, with a 49% decrease. In contrast, the most minor decrease occurred in genotype Kav 210, with a 13% reduction (Table 1 and Fig. 1).

In the roots, the highest decrease in P content under drought stress compared to the control was again observed in genotype Kav 20 (45% decrease), while the lowest decrease was found in genotype Kav 252 (12% decrease). Under drought conditions, the P content of genotypes Kav 20 (0.32%) and Kav 183 (0.36%) approached the lower sufficiency threshold reported by Jones et al. [21] (0.30–0.80%), while the other genotypes maintained phosphorus levels within sufficient ranges (Table 2; Fig. 2).

Table 1. Macroelement contents in stem parts of melon genotypes

MACRO ELEMENTS (STEM)																	
Element	Treatment	Kav 8	Kav 20	Kav 28	Kav 62	Kav 70	Kav 183	Kav 188	Kav 190	Kav 204	Kav 210	Kav 231	Kav 248	Kav 257	Kav 265	Kav 267	Ortalama
P (%)	Control	0.90 cd	0.63 g	0.74 fg	0.91 bc	1.10 a	0.62 g	0.84 c-f	0.88 cde	0.89 cde	0.76 ef	0.78 def	0.77 def	0.62 g	0.89 cde	1.03 ab	0.82 a
	Drought	0.72 b	0.32 e	0.64 bc	0.59 cd	0.88 a	0.36 e	0.62 bc	0.72 b	0.69 b	0.66 bc	0.51 d	0.62 bc	0.51 d	0.72 b	0.72 b	0.62 b
	Change	-20	-49	-14	-36	-21	-41	-26	-19	-22	-13	-34	-20	-18	-19	-30	
	Mean	0.81 bc	0.47 h	0.69 efg	0.75 cde	0.99 a	0.49 h	0.73 c-f	0.80 bcd	0.79 bcd	0.71 def	0.64 fg	0.69 ef	0.56 gh	0.80 bcd	0.87 b	
K (%)	Control	4.15 bc	2.89 fg	3.82 cd	3.89 c	3.18 efg	3.14 e-h	2.80gh	2.76 h	3.10 e-h	3.41 e	3.45 e	5.11 a	3.22 ef	4.53 b	4.14 c	3.57 a
	Drought	3.45 c	1.92 j	2.81 ef	3.04 de	2.11 ij	2.26 hi	2.61 fg	2.4 gh	2.79 ef	3.31 cd	2.81 ef	4.58 a	3.05 de	3.85 b	3.13 d	2.94 b
	Change	-17	-34	-26	-22	-34	-28	-7	-13	-10	-3	-18	-10	-5	-15	-24	
	Mean	3.80 c	2.41 j	3.32 ef	3.47 de	2.65 ij	2.70 hi	2.70hi	2.58 ij	2.95 gh	3.36 ef	3.13 fg	4.85 a	3.14 fg	4.19 b	3.64 cd	
Ca (%)	Control	3.16 a	3.15 a	2.57 a	3.35 a	3.01 a	2.78 a	2.92 a	2.42 a	3.22 a	2.54 a	2.70 a	3.00 a	2.34 a	2.72 a	2.25 a	2.81 a
	Drought	2.01 bcde	1.33 ef	2.08 abcde	2.11 abcd	1.38 def	2.07 abcde	2.59 ab	2.01 bcde	2.68 ab	2.16 abc	2.02 abcde	2.78 a	1.99 bcdef	1.62 cdef	1.24 f	2.00 b
	Change	-36	-58	-19	-37	-54	-26	-11	-17	-17	-15	-25	-7	-15	-41	-45	
	Mean	2.59 a	2.24 ab	2.33 ab	2.73 a	2.19 ab	2.43 ab	2.75 a	2.21 ab	2.95 a	2.35 ab	2.36 ab	2.89 a	2.16 ab	2.17 ab	1.75 b	
Mg (%)	Control	0.37 a	0.33 a-d	0.32 b-e	0.33 bcd	0.34 ab	0.30 de	0.33 a-d	0.31 b-e	0.34 ab	0.33 b-e	0.33 a-d	0.30 b-e	0.30 cde	0.34 abc	0.29 e	0.32 a
	Drought	0.31 a	0.21 fg	0.21 fg	0.28 abc	0.25 cde	0.21 fg	0.24 ef	0.24 def	0.29 ab	0.30 a	0.26 bcde	0.28 abcd	0.21 fg	0.28 abc	0.19 g	0.25 b
	Change	-16	-37	-34	-15	-27	-30	-27	-22	-14	-8	-21	-8	-30	-17	-34	
	Mean	0.34 a	0.27 efg	0.27 fgh	0.30 bcd	0.30 b-e	0.25 gh	0.29 c-f	0.28 d-g	0.32 ab	0.32 ab	0.30 b-e	0.29 b-f	0.25 gh	0.31 bc	0.24 h	
S (%)	Control	0.69 bc	0.47 h	0.61 d	0.69 b	0.52 fg	0.55 ef	0.34 j	0.43 i	0.52 fg	0.70 b	0.61 d	0.78 a	0.65 c	0.57 e	0.49 gh	0.57 a
	Drought	0.48 cd	0.35 g	0.53 b	0.25 i	0.28 hi	0.43 ef	0.27 hi	0.39 f	0.42 ef	0.59 a	0.48 cd	0.52 bc	0.41 f	0.46 de	0.30 h	0.41 b
	Change	-30	-26	-14	-64	-46	-22	-20	0	-20	-16	-21	-33	-37	-19	-39	
	Mean	0.59 b	0.41g	0.57 bc	0.47 f	0.40 g	0.49 ef	0.31 h	0.41 g	0.47 f	0.64 a	0.55 cd	0.65 a	0.53 d	0.52 de	0.39 g	

The potassium (K) content in the stem parts of melon genotypes decreased by 18% under drought conditions (2.94% K) compared to the control (3.57% K). Among the melon genotypes, the most significant reductions in potassium content were observed in genotypes Kav 20 and Kav 70, both showing a 34% decrease. The least reductions were seen in genotypes Kav 210 (3%) and Kav 257 (5%) under drought conditions (Table 1 and Fig. 1). In the roots, the decrease in potassium levels in the PEG 6000-induced drought stress group ranged from 2% to 39% compared to the control. The most significant decrease was observed in genotype Kav 70 (39%), while the most minor decrease was observed in genotype Kav 183 (2%). Among the genotypes subjected to drought stress, the highest potassium content was found in genotype Kav 248 (5.90%). According to the sufficiency threshold reported by Jones et al. [21] (4.00–5.00% K), only genotype Kav 248 (4.58% K) maintained sufficient potassium levels under drought conditions. In contrast, all other genotypes fell within the deficiency range (Table 2 and Fig. 2).

Under drought stress conditions, the melon genotypes' calcium (Ca) content reduced from 58% to 7% compared to the control treatment. Among the genotypes, the highest calcium content under drought stress was observed in genotype Kav 248 (2.78%). In contrast, the lowest calcium contents were found in genotypes Kav 267 (1.24%) and Kav 20 (1.33%) (Table 1 and Fig. 1). In the roots, the highest change was a 49% decrease in genotype Kav 20, while the lowest change was a 5% reduction in genotype Kav 248. According to the sufficiency threshold values reported by Jones et al. [21] (2.30–3.00% Ca), the calcium content in genotypes Kav 188 (2.59%), Kav 204 (2.68%), and Kav 248 (2.78%) was within the sufficiency range, while all other genotypes had calcium contents within the deficiency range (Table 2 and Fig. 2).

The magnesium (Mg) content of plants subjected to drought stress decreased from 37% to 8% compared to the control treatment. Among the melon genotypes, the most significant reductions in magnesium content were recorded in genotypes Kav 20, Kav 28, and Kav 267, while the most minor reductions were observed in genotypes Kav 248 and Kav 210 (Table 1 and Fig. 1)

In the roots, the percentage change in magnesium content compared to the control ranged from 42% to 22%. The most significant reduction was observed in genotype Kav 70, while genotype Kav 248 had the value closest to the control. According to the sufficiency threshold values reported by Jones et al. [21] (0.35–0.80% Mg), the magnesium contents of all the genotypes used in the study were below the sufficiency threshold and within the deficiency range (Table 2 and Fig. 2).

The sulfur (S) content of the melon genotypes under drought conditions showed a reduction ranging from 64% to 0% compared to the control treatment, with the highest reductions observed in genotypes Kav 62 and Kav 70. According to the sufficiency threshold values for sulfur reported by Jones et al. [22] (0.25–1.4% S), the sulfur contents of all genotypes under drought conditions were within the sufficiency range (Table 2 and Fig. 2).

Drought stress significantly affects the bioavailability and uptake of nutrients in plants. This study examined the changes in macro-nutrient elements such as phosphorus (P), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and sulfur (S) in melon genotypes under drought stress. The findings suggest that all of these macro-nutrients decreased under drought conditions, and this decrease is directly related to the plant's growth parameters.

Table 2. Macro element contents in root parts of melon genotypes

MAKRO ELEMENTS (ROOT)																	
Element	Treatment	Kav 8	Kav 20	Kav 28	Kav 62	Kav 70	Kav 183	Kav 188	Kav 190	Kav 204	Kav 210	Kav 231	Kav 248	Kav 257	Kav 265	Kav 267	Ortalama
P (%)	Control	0.82 b-f	0.72 efg	0.77 c-g	0.85 b-e	0.88 bcd	0.49 h	1.15 a	0.92 bc	0.98 b	0.81 c-f	0.86 b-e	0.91 bc	0.64 gh	0.68 fg	0.73 d-g	0.81 a
	Drought	0.62 abc	0.40 d	0.64 abc	0.55 c	0.63 abc	0.38 d	0.69 ab	0.69 a	0.59 bc	0.59 bc	0.62 abc	0.71 a	0.56 c	0.56 c	0.59 bc	0.59 b
	Change	-25	-45	-17	-35	-29	-23	-39	-25	-40	-26	-28	-23	-12	-17	-19	
	Mean	0.72 b-f	0.56 h	0.71 c-f	0.70 d-g	0.75 bcd	0.44 l	0.92 a	0.81 bc	0.78 bcd	0.70 d-g	0.74 b-e	0.81 b	0.60 gh	0.62 fgh	0.66 efg	
K (%)	Control	5.01 d	3.94 fg	4.32 ef	4.59 e	5.18 d	2.28 h	6.95 a	3.70 g	4.47 e	4.22 ef	4.61 e	6.99 a	3.98 fg	6.06 b	5.62 c	4.79 a
	Drought	3.98 cde	2.52 h	3.34 fg	4.12 cd	3.18 g	2.23 h	4.85 b	3.29 fg	3.34 fg	3.77 def	4.21 cd	5.90 a	3.47 efg	4.35 bc	3.79 cdef	3.76 b
	Change	-21	-36	-23	-10	-39	-2	-30	-11	-25	-11	-9	-16	-13	-28	-33	
	Mean	4.50 de	3.23 j	3.83 gh ₁	4.35 def	4.18 efg	2.26 k	5.90 b	3.50 ij	3.90 gh	3.99 fgh	4.41 de	6.44 a	3.72 h ₁	5.21 c	4.70 d	
Ca (%)	Control	0.52 de	0.40 fg	0.52 de	0.51 de	0.53 cde	0.63 ab	0.62 abc	0.44 efg	0.49 def	0.56 bcd	0.39 g	0.70 a	0.50 de	0.48 def	0.52 de	0.52 a
	Drought	0.35 efg	0.21 h	0.41 cde	0.37 defg	0.29 g	0.49 b	0.46 bc	0.32 fg	0.38 cdef	0.43 bcd	0.29 g	0.67 a	0.43 bcd	0.35 efg	0.33 efg	0.39 b
	Change	-33	-49	-21	-26	-45	-22	-26	-27	-22	-23	-25	-5	-13	-28	-36	
	Mean	0.30 cde	0.30 g	0.46 cd	0.44 cde	0.41 de	0.56 b	0.54 b	0.38 ef	0.44 cde	0.50 bc	0.34 fg	0.69 a	0.47 cd	0.41 de	0.42 de	
Mg (%)	Control	0.29 d-h	0.39 b	0.30 d-g	0.31 def	0.28 e-h	0.32 cde	0.63 a	0.27 e-h	0.25 gh	0.26 fgh	0.33 cd	0.37 bc	0.29 d-h	0.24 h	0.25 gh	0.32 a
	Drought	0.20 d	0.25 c	0.19 de	0.19 de	0.16 e	0.21 d	0.40 a	0.21 d	0.19 de	0.18 de	0.21 d	0.29 b	0.19 de	0.18 de	0.18 de	0.22 b
	Change	-32	-35	-36	-39	-42	-34	-37	-23	-24	-32	-37	-22	-34	-24	-28	
	Mean	0.25 cde	0.32 b	0.25 cde	0.25 cd	0.22 de	0.27 c	0.52 a	0.24 cde	0.22 de	0.22 de	0.27 c	0.33 b	0.24 cde	0.21 e	0.22 de	
S (%)	Control	0.61 cde	0.32 j	0.54 fgh	0.51 gh	0.71 b	0.32 j	0.67 bc	0.43 i	0.58 ef	0.49 h	0.61 de	0.79 a	0.60 def	0.64 cd	0.55 efg	0.56 a
	Drought	0.36 ef	0.23 g	0.39 def	0.39 def	0.41 cde	0.23 g	0.44 abcd	0.41 bcde	0.39 def	0.41 cde	0.43 abcd	0.48 a	0.34 f	0.47 ab	0.47 abc	0.39 b
	Change	-41	-28	-28	-23	-42	-28	-35	-4	-33	-17	-29	-39	-44	-26	-15	
	Mean	0.49 def	0.27 h	0.47 efg	0.45 fg	0.56 b	0.28 h	0.55 bc	0.42 g	0.48 def	0.45 fg	0.52 bcd	0.63 a	0.47 efg	0.56 bc	0.51 cde	

Phosphorus plays a critical role in energy storage and transport in plants and in the transport and storage of metabolic substances like sugars and starch [22]. It also involves vital biological processes such as cell division and genetic material transmission. The most prominent was the 49% reduction in phosphorus content under drought conditions observed in the Kav 20 genotype. Similarly, it was determined that with the increase in drought stress, the availability of phosphorus (P) in the soil decreased, reducing the phosphorus content in melon genotypes [23]. Decreased phosphorus means that plants cannot provide the energy required for cell division and growth, hindering growth processes. Therefore, the reductions in growth parameters observed under drought stress may be attributed to phosphorus deficiency. Furthermore, due to phosphorus deficiency, plants struggle to produce energy, disrupting the cell's ionic balance [24].

A decrease of up to 34% in potassium (K) content was observed under drought stress. Potassium is an essential element that plays a role in regulating intercellular water balance, maintaining osmotic pressure, and participating in fundamental functions such as photosynthesis [25]. Potassium deficiency can disrupt intracellular osmotic balance and limit the plant's ability to retain water. This results in the disruption of the water balance within the cell and a loss of turgor, making the plant more sensitive to drought stress [24]. Additionally, potassium deficiency affects mechanisms that regulate water uptake and distribution within cells, leading to a higher susceptibility to water loss. The inability of plants to properly absorb and distribute water results in developmental retardation. In a study conducted by Kiran et al. [26], it was reported that drought stress decreased potassium content, negatively impacting osmotic pressure and limiting growth parameters [26]. Similarly, in drought stress, melon genotypes' potassium content decreased by approximately 10% [27]. Since water stress prevents plants from absorbing nutrients from their growth environment, these deficiencies lead to reductions in growth parameters [28]. Potassium regulates osmotic pressure within cells, ensuring water balance in plants and also playing a role in fundamental metabolic processes such as photosynthesis [25].

Furthermore, reducing potassium under drought stress may cause plants to exhibit lower resistance to drought conditions. Potassium (K) and calcium (Ca) are known to be two key elements that increase plant tolerance to drought stress [29]. A study conducted by Kiran et al. [26], reported that drought stress decreased the levels of potassium and calcium ions in plants, with a more significant reduction observed in the Ananas genotype compared to the Semame genotype. Similarly, a study by Bagheri et al. [23], also found reductions in potassium content in melon plants under drought stress [23]. These findings suggest that drought stress affects the plant's intracellular water balance, limiting the uptake of nutrients such as potassium and calcium.

Calcium (Ca) strengthens the structure of cell walls in plants, regulates cell membrane permeability, and is essential for cell division [29]. In the present study, a decrease of up to 58% in calcium content was observed in melon genotypes subjected to drought stress. The most significant reduction was detected in the Kav 20 genotype. Calcium plays an important role in maintaining water balance by preserving the structural integrity of cell walls. The cell wall serves as the first line of defense against water loss in plants, and calcium is a critical component in strengthening this structure. Calcium deficiency increases cell membrane permeability, accelerating water loss, which makes plants more vulnerable to drought stress. Calcium also plays an important role in maintaining cell turgor; therefore, its deficiency can lead to turgor loss and disrupt water balance in plants. Calcium deficiency can increase cell membrane permeability, accelerate water loss, and exacerbate ionic imbalances within cells. In melon plants under drought stress, the observed reductions in calcium content weakened the plants' ability to maintain water balance and resulted in turgor loss [30]. These findings highlight the

role of calcium in enhancing plant resistance to drought stress. Furthermore, in a study conducted by Hamurcu et al. [28], reductions in calcium content under drought stress were also detected in two watermelon genotypes.

Magnesium, the central atom of chlorophyll, is critically important for photosynthesis. A 37% reduction in magnesium content under drought can reduce the photosynthetic efficiency of plants, thus limiting their growth rate. Bagheri et al. [23] mentioned that as the dose of drought stress increased, reductions in magnesium content were also observed [23]. Similarly, in a study by Hamurcu et al. [28], reductions in magnesium content were detected in two watermelon genotypes under drought stress, compared to the control group.

Changes in Micro Nutrient Content

The changes in the micronutrient content of root and stem samples of melon genotypes under drought stress conditions were examined. The results indicate a significant decreasing trend in the content of these elements due to drought stress. Considering the averages of the genotypes used in the study, the most considerable reductions in micronutrient content in both root and stem samples under drought conditions, compared to the control, were observed in manganese (Mn), zinc (Zn), iron (Fe), and copper (Cu) contents.

Fig. 3. Average reduction rates of Micronutrients in Stem parts based on the mean of melon genotypes

Fig. 4. Average reduction rates of Micronutrients in Root parts based on the mean of melon genotypes

Under drought stress, a significant decrease in total iron content was observed in the stem samples of 15 melon genotypes compared to the control. The reduction in iron content ranged from 3% to 47%, with the greatest decrease observed in the Kav 188 genotype (47% reduction) (Table 3 and Fig. 3). The reduction in the roots varied between 3% and 49%.

Table 3. *Microelement contents in stem parts of melon genotypes*

MICROELEMENTS (STEM)																	
Element	Treatment	Kav 8	Kav 20	Kav 28	Kav 62	Kav 70	Kav 183	Kav 188	Kav 190	Kav 204	Kav 210	Kav 231	Kav 248	Kav 257	Kav 265	Kav 267	Ortalama
Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	162.62 h	184.83 e	181.70 ef	189.71 d	201.27 c	128.26 k	201.94 c	232.97 a	181.54 f	162.81 h	154.45 i	163.45 h	145.50 j	171.10 g	213.60 b	178.38 a
	Drought	156.94 c	145.61 d	117.90 f	146.95 d	164.15 b	108.78 g	107.94 g	161.04 b	172.81 a	119.54 f	128.07 e	148.29 d	109.57 g	93.53 h	147.47 d	135.24 b
	Change	-3	-21	-35	-23	-18	-15	-47	-31	-5	-27	-17	-9	-25	-45	-31	
	Mean	159.78 f	165.22 e	149.80 h	168.33 d	182.71 b	118.52 i	154.90 g	197.00 a	177.18 c	141.18 i	141.26 i	155.87 g	127.54 k	132.30 j	180.50 b	
Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	26.60 bc	21.43 efg	20.87 efg	21.36 efg	25.21 cd	20.47 efg	29.10 b	22.77 def	19.98 fg	16.10 i	23.38 de	19.47 gh	16.83 hi	20.47 efg	37.95 a	22.80 a
	Drought	24.52 b	16.37 ef	12.61 h	17.15 def	19.81 c	15.06 fgh	19.51 cd	18.38 cde	17.05 def	13.37 gh	17.10 def	15.35 fg	16.08 ef	15.08 fgh	32.36 a	17.99 b
	Change	-8	-24	-40	-20	-21	-26	-33	-19	-15	-17	-27	-21	-4	-26	-15	
	Mean	25.56 b	18.90 efg	16.74 ghi	19.26 ef	22.51 cd	17.77 fgh	24.31 bc	20.57 de	18.52 e-h	14.74 i	20.24 e	17.41 fgh	16.45 hi	17.78 fgh	35.15 a	
Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	27.90 bc	21.11 fgh	18.50 hi	25.34 cde	33.00 a	23.32 def	13.23 k	28.46 b	20.16 gh	15.44 jk	18.32 hij	25.87 bcd	17.06 ij	22.69 efg	21.92 fg	22.15 a
	Drought	16.62 bc	14.81 cde	13.80 def	14.81 cde	22.81 a	16.02 cd	12.06 fg	14.24 cdef	18.89 b	11.07 g	15.03 cde	13.45 defg	14.96 cde	12.69 efg	16.65 bc	15.19 b
	Change	-40	-30	-25	-42	-31	-31	-9	-50	-6	-28	-18	-48	-12	-44	-24	
	Mean	22.26 b	17.96 def	16.15 f	20.07 bcd	27.90 a	19.67 cde	12.65 g	21.35 bc	19.52 cde	13.25 g	16.67 f	19.66 cde	16.01 f	17.69 ef	19.28 cde	
B (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	41.17 e	26.39 l	37.30 fgh	54.41 b	38.29 efg	34.65 hij	35.97 ghi	61.89 a	44.88 d	31.26 jk	40.49 ef	23.92 l	31.07 k	33.58 ijk	49.18 c	38.96 a
	Drought	35.49 de	21.37 j	25.77 hi	35.14 de	24.28 ij	29.41 fgh	26.13 ghi	46.75 a	43.74 ab	29.93 fg	35.95 cd	20.53 j	25.97 ghi	31.67 ef	39.90 bc	31.47 b
	Change	-14	-19	-31	-35	-37	-15	-27	-24	-3	-4	-11	-14	-16	-6	-19	
	Mean	38.33 c	23.88 f	31.54 d	44.77 b	31.28 de	32.03 d	31.05 de	54.32 a	44.31 b	30.59 de	38.22 c	22.23 f	28.52 e	32.63 d	44.54 b	
Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	7.47 bc	9.39 ab	9.12 b	7.21 bc	7.64 bc	5.85 c	9.33 ab	9.52 ab	9.61 ab	6.82 bc	7.46 bc	9.39 ab	7.65 bc	7.42 bc	12.09 a	8.40 a
	Drought	6.51 bcd	5.14 cd	5.61 cd	5.36 cd	6.14 cd	5.39 cd	5.29 cd	8.11 ab	5.10 cd	6.28 bcd	4.56 d	6.94 bc	6.06 cd	5.38 cd	9.58 a	6.10 b
	Change	-13	-45	-38	-26	-20	-8	-43	-15	-47	-8	-39	-26	-21	-28	-21	
	Mean	6.99 bcd	7.26 bcd	7.37 bcd	6.29 cd	6.89 bcd	5.62 d	7.31 bcd	8.81 b	7.36 bcd	6.55 cd	6.01 d	8.17 bc	6.86 cd	6.40 cd	10.84 a	

The highest iron content in the drought-stressed group was found in the Kav 248 genotype, with 799.78 mg kg⁻¹ of iron. According to the sufficiency threshold values for iron (50-300 mg kg⁻¹) reported by Jones et al. [21], all the genotypes used in the study had iron contents within the sufficiency range (Table 4 and Fig. 4). Kiran et al. [26] noted that iron is one of the elements that decreases under abiotic stress conditions, and they observed a negative correlation between leaf water potential and the reduction in iron, especially in plants like melon [26]. Previous studies have shown that iron levels decrease under drought stress, negatively affecting plant growth and development [31].

In the study, a decrease in zinc content was also observed in the melon genotypes under drought stress, with the reduction rates ranging from 40% to 4%. The most significant decrease was measured in the Kav 28 genotype, while the smallest decrease was observed in the Kav 257 genotype (Table 3 and Fig. 3). In the roots, the changes under drought stress ranged from a 63% decrease in the Kav 231 genotype to a 7% decrease in the Kav 257 genotype. Under drought stress, the zinc content in the melon genotypes was compared to the sufficiency threshold values for zinc (20-200 mg kg⁻¹) reported by Jones et al. [21]. The zinc contents of the Kav 8 (24.52 mg kg⁻¹) and Kav 267 (32.36 mg kg⁻¹) genotypes were found to be within the sufficiency range, while the zinc contents of all other genotypes were within the deficiency range (Table 4 and Fig. 4). Kiran et al. [30] reported that zinc absorption changes negatively under drought stress, and this negatively affects the plants' overall water absorption and mineral nutrition. Drought stress has also been reported to decrease zinc content in other plants, such as corn [32] and beans [33]. This indicates that under drought conditions, the reduced uptake of zinc by plants limits their growth parameters, highlighting the vital importance of this ion for plant health.

The manganese content in melon genotypes showed a general decrease under drought conditions compared to the control. Decreases ranged from 50% to 6%, with the greatest decrease observed in the Kav 190 genotype and the most minor decrease in the Kav 204 genotype (Table 3 and Fig. 3). In the roots of the plants, the decrease ranged from 75% in the Kav 70 genotype to 7% in the Kav 248 genotype. The manganese content of the melon genotypes under drought stress was compared to the sufficiency threshold values for manganese (50-250 mg kg⁻¹) reported by Jones et al. [21]. It was determined that the manganese content of all genotypes was within the deficiency threshold values (Table 4 and Fig. 4). Kiran et al. [26], related the observed decrease in manganese content under drought stress to the photosynthesis and other enzymatic reactions in plants. Similarly, manganese deficiency can negatively affect essential physiological processes such as carbohydrate metabolism and respiration, making plants more sensitive to drought stress.

The boron content of the melon genotypes also decreased under drought conditions compared to the control, with decreases ranging from 37% to 3%. The most significant decrease was observed in the Kav 70 genotype, while the smallest decrease was in the Kav 204 genotype (Table 3 and Fig. 3). In the roots, the decrease in boron content ranged from 8% in the Kav 62 genotype to 56% in the Kav 70 genotype. The boron content of the melon genotypes under drought stress was compared to the sufficiency threshold values for boron (25-60 mg kg⁻¹) reported by Jones et al. [21]. The Kav 20 (21.37 mg kg⁻¹), Kav 70 (24.28 mg kg⁻¹), and Kav 248 (20.53 mg kg⁻¹) genotypes were found to be within the deficiency range, while the boron content of all other genotypes was within the sufficiency range (Table 4 and Fig. 4).

The copper content in the melon genotypes also decreased under drought conditions compared to the control, with decreases ranging from 47% to 8%. The greatest decrease was observed in the Kav 204 genotype, while the smallest decrease was in the Kav 210 genotype (Table 3 and Fig. 3). In the drought-stressed group, the highest copper content in the roots was 22.16 mg kg⁻¹ in the Kav 257 genotype.

Table 4. *Microelement contents in root parts of melon genotypes*

MICROELEMENTS (ROOT)																	
Element	Treatment	Kav 8	Kav 20	Kav 28	Kav 62	Kav 70	Kav 183	Kav 188	Kav 190	Kav 204	Kav 210	Kav 231	Kav 248	Kav 257	Kav 265	Kav 267	Ortalama
Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	602.74 c	314.15 n	499.28 h	526.69 f	827.99 b	355.65 m	496.43 i	403.77 l	489.01 j	516.43 g	564.99 d	932.65 a	437.61 k	547.96 e	401.20 i	527.80 a
	Drought	464.39 e	202.62 n	253.67 m	340.63 ij	493.41 b	318.99 k	483.63 c	392.16 h	468.51 d	339.27 j	427.42 f	799.78 a	342.84 i	402.53 g	296.73 i	401.80 b
	Change	-23	-36	-49	-35	-40	-10	-3	-3	-4	-34	-24	-14	-22	-27	-26	
	Mean	533.60 c	258.40 o	376.50 i	433.70 h	660.70 b	337.32 n	490.03 e	397.97 j	478.76 f	427.80 i	496.20 d	866.20 a	390.20 k	475.20 g	349.00 m	
Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	63.15 e	33.82 h	53.66 f	84.51 b	105.71 a	37.23 gh	71.22 d	33.53 h	57.05 e	34.17 h	68.71 d	68.11 d	56.52 f	39.22 g	76.01 c	58.84 a
	Drought	41.94 c	24.21 i	30.12 fg	36.41 d	44.68 bc	31.98 ef	32.65 ef	28.37 gh	34.10 de	21.07 j	25.76 hi	44.69 bc	52.48 a	14.42 k	45.39 b	33.88 b
	Change	-34	-28	-44	-57	-58	-14	-54	-15	-40	-38	-63	-34	-7	-63	-40	
	Mean	52.54 d	29.01 hi	41.89 f	60.50 b	75.20 a	34.60 g	51.94 d	30.95 h	45.58 e	27.62 i	47.24 e	56.40 c	54.50 cd	26.82 i	60.70 b	
Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	108.42 e	29.80 i	62.52 j	82.99 h	413.67 a	40.90 k	28.46 l	114.37 d	171.74 c	89.95 g	94.88 f	67.68 i	94.08 f	235.58 b	67.01 i	113.50 a
	Drought	51.62 f	14.21 j	45.11 g	59.70 e	102.57 a	23.85 i	16.45 j	52.36 f	89.07 b	61.28 e	65.55 cd	63.10 de	68.32 c	68.94 c	37.79 h	54.66 b
	Change	-52	-50	-29	-28	-75	-42	-42	-54	-48	-32	-31	-7	-27	-71	-44	
	Mean	80.00 e	22.01 k	53.82 i	71.34 g	258.10 a	32.37 j	22.46 k	83.40 d	130.40 c	75.61 f	80.22 e	65.39 h	81.20 de	152.3 b	52.40 i	
B (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	28.05 cd	15.38 g	24.51 def	27.20 cd	34.31 a	21.45 f	32.70ab	16.60 g	28.02 cd	25.57 de	30.74 bc	21.23 f	22.06 ef	26.90 d	27.57 cd	25.49 a
	Drought	15.37 def	12.20 h	18.85 bc	25.15 a	14.93 defg	15.49 def	17.26 cd	13.79 fgh	15.4 def	14.52 efgh	20.67 b	12.45 gh	16.92 cde	14.09 fgh	16.99 cde	16.27 b
	Change	-45	-21	-23	-8	-56	-28	-47	-17	-45	-43	-33	-41	-23	-48	-38	
	Mean	21.71 cd	13.79 h	21.68 cd	26.18 a	24.62 ab	18.47 ef	24.98 a	15.19 gh	21.71 cd	20.05 cde	25.70 a	16.84 fg	19.49 de	20.50 cde	22.28 bc	
Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	Control	19.22 i	30.47 e	22.74 h	34.78 cd	50.62 a	26.43 fg	23.86 gh	18.04 ij	35.66 c	15.89 j	40.41 b	31.94 de	29.41 ef	17.24 ij	24.73 gh	28.10 a
	Drought	10.83 fg	13.02 efg	16.3 bcd	13.94 def	18.43 b	14.83 cde	18.06 bc	11.96 efg	19.22 ab	10.55 g	13.83 def	13.18 defg	22.16 a	10.24 g	16.34 bcd	14.86 b
	Change	-44	-57	-28	-60	-64	-44	-24	-34	-46	-34	-66	-59	-25	-41	-34	
	Mean	15.03 g	21.75 ef	19.52 f	24.36 cd	34.53 a	20.63 ef	20.96 ef	15.00 g	27.44 b	13.22 g	27.12 b	22.56 de	25.78 bc	13.74 g	20.53 ef	

The change rates compared to the control ranged from a 24% to a 66% decrease. The copper content of the melon genotypes under drought stress was compared to the sufficiency threshold values for copper (7-30 mg kg⁻¹) reported by Jones et al. [21], and it was determined that the copper content of all genotypes was within the deficiency threshold values (Table 4 and Fig. 4).

CONCLUSION

The results of our study revealed significant differences in the macro-nutrient content of melon genotypes under drought stress conditions. Considering the average values of the genotypes, the elements that showed the greatest reduction in concentration compared to the control were found to be phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), and sulfur (S). Among the melon genotypes used in the study, the Kav 20 genotype exhibited the greatest decrease in phosphorus, potassium, calcium, and magnesium values. This genotype can be considered one of the most determining factors in the low level of drought stress tolerance, as it showed significant reductions in these macro-nutrients. The deficiency of elements, especially phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and calcium (Ca), in the plant body reduces water use efficiency and makes it more difficult for the plant to survive under drought conditions. These elements contribute to the proper functioning of antioxidant systems in the plant and thus facilitate the combat against oxidative stress caused by drought. In addition, deficiencies in P, K, and Ca collectively negatively affect cell division, elongation, and differentiation, leading to a slowdown in the plant's growth and development. The reductions in P, K, and Ca concentrations observed under drought stress conditions in melon genotypes adversely affect water uptake, cellular integrity, energy metabolism, and stress responses in the plant. These changes indicate that the plant's resistance to drought is significantly weakened. The ability of different melon genotypes to maintain these elements under drought conditions may play an important role in their drought tolerance mechanisms. The differences in drought tolerance among the genotypes used in our study suggest that the nutrient content and the ability to maintain the sufficiency levels of these nutrients directly and indirectly affect their tolerance to drought stress [19].

Similar negative effects on the micronutrient content of the genotypes under drought conditions have been observed. When considering the averages of the genotypes, it has been determined that the largest decreases in micronutrient content compared to the control under drought conditions are in the concentrations of Mn, Zn, Fe, and Cu. Especially the Kav 183 and Kav 190 genotypes were more adversely affected due to the significant decrease in iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn) content. The Kav 248 and Kav 265 genotypes showed less decrease in these elements compared to the control under drought conditions, demonstrating greater resilience.

Micronutrients in plants, particularly Fe, Zn, and Mn, are components of various antioxidant enzymes (SOD, catalase, peroxidase). Deficiencies in these micronutrients significantly limit the capacity to combat oxidative damage caused by drought. These three elements also play critical roles in photosynthetic activity. Their deficiencies reduce the plant's energy production and, thus, its ability to grow and adapt to stressful conditions. The lack of these elements disrupts the physiological mechanisms regulating water uptake and transport, making water management more difficult for the plant under drought conditions. Deficiencies in Fe, Zn, and Mn affect root development and structure, hindering efficient water uptake under limited water conditions. These elements play a role in the signal transduction pathways necessary for stress detection and response activation. Their deficiencies prevent the plant from responding quickly and effectively to drought stress. The reduction of micronutrients such as Fe, Zn, and Mn in melon genotypes under drought stress conditions negatively affects the plant's fundamental physiological processes (photosynthesis, antioxidant defense, water metabolism, growth, and development), thereby reducing its drought resistance. Ensuring the adequate maintenance or supplementation of these elements under drought conditions may be an important strategy in increasing drought tolerance in melon cultivation. Differences in the ability of different melon genotypes to maintain these

micronutrients under drought conditions could help explain why some genotypes are more drought-resistant than others [10].

Results of our research, highlight the restrictive effects of drought stress on plant growth and development processes and the differences between genotypes. The selection of resistant genotypes is critical for plant health. It is understood that the deficiency of both macro and micronutrients under drought conditions decreases the plants' resistance to drought stress and weakens their adaptation capacity.

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